

IQTISODIYOT & TARAQQIYOT

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PRAGMATIC AND DERIVATIONAL CHANGES OF THE UZBEK LANGUAGE IN YOUTH SPEECH (BASED ON SOCIAL MEDIA AND MEDIA TEXTS)

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Abstract: This article analyzes pragmatic and derivational changes occurring in the speech of Uzbek-speaking youth, using a corpus of social media and media texts from 2022–2026. The study draws on a 300,000-word corpus of comments on Telegram, Instagram, and YouTube, as well as 500 media texts from online publications targeting youth. The results demonstrate that youth speech is not a simplified or corrupted version of standard Uzbek, but a creative laboratory where new linguistic forms emerge and spread.

Keywords: youth speech, pragmatic changes, derivational changes, social media, Uzbek language, word-formation, language innovation, digital communication.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada o'zbek tilidagi yoshlar nutqida yuz berayotgan pragmatik va derivatsion o'zgarishlar ijtimoiy tarmoqlar va ommaviy axborot vositalari matnlari asosida tahlil qilinadi. Tadqiqot 2022–2026-yillardagi Telegram, Instagram va YouTube'dagi sharhlar hamda yoshlarga mo'ljallangan onlayn nashrlarning 300 000 so'zdan iborat korpusiga tayanadi. Natijalar shuni ko'rsatadiki, yoshlar nutqi standart o'zbek tilining soddalashgan yoki buzilgan versiyasi emas, balki yangi lingvistik shakllar paydo bo'ladigan va tarqaladigan ijodiy laboratoriya vazifasini o'taydi.

Kalit so'zlar: yoshlar nutqi, pragmatik o'zgarishlar, derivatsion o'zgarishlar, ijtimoiy tarmoqlar, o'zbek tili, so'z yasalishi, til innovatsiyalari, raqamli muloqot.

Аннотация: В данной статье анализируются прагматические и деривационные изменения, происходящие в речи узбекскоязычной молодежи, на основе корпуса текстов социальных сетей и медиа за 2022–2026 годы. Исследование опирается на корпус объемом 300 000 слов из комментариев в Telegram, Instagram и YouTube, а также 500 медиатекстов из онлайн-изданий, ориентированных на молодежь. Результаты показывают, что молодежная речь — это не упрощенная или испорченная версия стандартного узбекского языка, а творческая лаборатория, в которой возникают и распространяются новые языковые формы.

Ключевые слова: молодежная речь, прагматические изменения, деривационные изменения, социальные сети, узбекский язык, словообразование, языковые инновации, цифровая коммуникация.

INTRODUCTION

Youth speech has long been recognized as a dynamic driver of language change. Unlike adult speech, which tends toward stability and adherence to normative standards, youth speech is characterized by innovation, playfulness, and sensitivity to social trends. In the digital era, these characteristics have been amplified by the affordances of social media platforms, which enable rapid dissemination of new linguistic forms and create novel communicative contexts. For the Uzbek language, the speech of young people aged 16–30 represents the frontline of ongoing linguistic transformation, yet it remains understudied compared to normative literary language or historical dialects.

The pragmatics of youth speech — how young speakers use language to achieve social goals, express attitudes, and construct identities — has shifted significantly under the influence of digital communication. Traditional face-to-face pragmatic strategies (politeness formulas, honorifics, indirect requests) are being adapted, abbreviated, or replaced by new strategies suited to the asynchronous, multi-participant, and visually

oriented environment of social media. Similarly, derivational processes — the formation of new words through affixation, compounding, and other mechanisms — are showing increased creativity and productivity in youth speech. Young Uzbek speakers are not merely borrowing words from English; they are actively creating new Uzbek words using both traditional and innovative patterns [1].

Linguistic research has established that youth speech is not a monolithic phenomenon but varies across age subgroups, platforms, and social contexts [2]. The pragmatic functions of youth speech — marking group identity, expressing solidarity or distance, performing humor or irony — are realized through specific linguistic features, including non-standard vocabulary, abbreviated forms, emotional punctuation and emojis, and innovative derivations. Understanding these features is essential for several practical reasons: educators need to know how to bridge the gap between classroom language and students' communicative reality; lexicographers must decide whether and how to document youth speech forms; and NLP developers require data on actual language use, not just normative standards [3].

This article addresses three research questions: (1) What major pragmatic changes characterize contemporary Uzbek youth speech on social media and in media texts? (2) What derivational patterns are particularly productive in youth speech, and how do they differ from standard Uzbek word-formation? (3) What sociolinguistic factors (age, gender, platform) correlate with variation in youth speech features? Based on a corpus of social media comments and online media texts from 2022–2026, the study provides a systematic analysis of these changes and discusses their implications for the broader Uzbek language.

REVIEW OF RELEVANT LITERATURE

The study of youth speech has a rich tradition in sociolinguistics, though the Uzbek context remains relatively underexplored. Existing literature can be organized into three streams: international research on youth language and digital communication, studies of Uzbek youth speech from the pre-digital era, and emerging work on Uzbek digital discourse.

Foundational work by Eckert demonstrated that youth speech is best understood through the concept of “communities of practice” – groups of young people who develop shared linguistic practices as part of their social identity construction [4]. More recently, Androutsopoulos has extended this framework to digital environments, showing that social media platforms create new affordances for youth language innovation, including multimodal expression (text, image, video) and accelerated diffusion of novel forms [2]. Research on pragmatic change in youth speech has identified several cross-linguistic trends: increased use of discourse markers (e.g., *like*, *well*, *so*), reduction of honorific distinctions in informal digital contexts, intensification of evaluative language (hyperbole, slang evaluatives), and the emergence of “ambient affiliation” – expressing stance without direct address [5]. These international findings provide a comparative baseline for the Uzbek case.

Prior to the widespread adoption of social media, research on Uzbek youth speech was limited and largely focused on urban dialects and slang. Sh. Rahmatullayev's dictionaries include some youth slang terms, primarily from Tashkent and Samarkand, but these were collected through traditional fieldwork methods and reflect the pre-digital era [6]. N. Mahmudov analyzed the speech of Uzbek university students in the early 2000s, identifying patterns of Russian-Uzbek code-mixing and the use of youth-specific evaluative adjectives (*zoʻr*, *ajoyib*, *dahshat* used positively) [7]. However, this research did not systematically address derivational innovation or the pragmatic functions of youth speech in informal contexts. A significant gap exists between the pre-digital studies and the current reality of social media-driven language change.

Recent years have seen growing attention to Uzbek language use on social media. Abdurakhmonova's corpus-based study of Instagram comments identified frequent use of English borrowings, emoticons, and non-standard orthography, but did not focus specifically on youth or on derivational patterns [3]. Yuldasheva has examined the formation of hybrid forms combining Uzbek suffixes with English roots (e.g., *like+la+moq*, *post+la+moq*), noting that these are particularly common among users under 25 [1]. However, no comprehensive study has yet analyzed both pragmatic and derivational changes in Uzbek youth speech systematically across multiple social media platforms. This study aims to fill that gap by providing a unified analysis of how young Uzbek speakers are reshaping their language in digital environments.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study employs a mixed-methods approach combining corpus linguistics, discourse analysis, and sociolinguistic variation analysis.

The primary data source is a specialized corpus of Uzbek youth speech compiled for this study, consisting of two components. First, a social media corpus of 300,000 words extracted from public posts and comments on three platforms: Telegram (channels and group chats popular among users aged 16–30), Instagram (posts and comment threads under youth-oriented accounts), and YouTube (comment sections under music, vlog, and entertainment content). Data were collected between January 2022 and December 2026, with sampling stratified by platform, gender, and estimated age. Second, a media text corpus of 500 texts (approximately 200,000 words) drawn from online youth-oriented publications, including *Daryo.uz* (youth sections), *Kun.uz* (blog and comment sections), and digital versions of magazines targeting young readers. All user-identifying information was removed prior to analysis.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

The findings are presented in two major sections: pragmatic changes and derivational changes, followed by an analysis of variation across social factors.

Three major pragmatic changes distinguish contemporary Uzbek youth speech from both standard literary Uzbek and the speech of older generations.

Young Uzbek speakers consistently reduce longer expressive sequences to shorter, often monosyllabic, forms. Standard Uzbek expressive phrases such as *Xudoyim, qanday zo'r!* (Oh God, how great!) appear in compressed form as *Alloh, zo'r!* or simply *Zo'r!* with multiple exclamation marks. Positive evaluation is frequently compressed to single intensifiers: *juda* (very) → *da, haqiqatan* (truly) → *haq*. This compression serves two pragmatic functions: it conveys urgency and authenticity (longer forms are perceived as overly formal or insincere), and it increases the speed of interaction in fast-paced digital exchanges. Compression is most extreme on platforms with character limits or rapid message turnover (Telegram chats, YouTube comments) and least common in more reflective contexts (Instagram captions, longer posts).

Youth speech exhibits a marked preference for intensified, often hyperbolic evaluation. Neutral or moderately positive expressions are avoided in favor of highly positive evaluatives: *yaxshi* (good) appears rarely; instead, *ajoyib* (amazing), *dahshat* (literally “terrible” but used positively to mean “awesome”), *toptirish* (perfect/matchless), *bomba* (the bomb), and *zo'r* (great/awesome) are frequent. Similarly, negative evaluation is intensified: *yomon* (bad) is replaced with *o'ta yomon* (extremely bad), *bema'ni* (nonsense), or *xafa qiladi* (it hurts) for milder criticism. Quantitative analysis shows that 73% of evaluative utterances in the youth corpus contain an intensifier, compared to an estimated 35% in standard written Uzbek. The pragmatic function is clear: in a noisy, attention-scarce digital environment, only intensified language captures attention and conveys a genuine stance.

Young speakers use language not just to convey information but also to perform identity in playful, often ironic ways. Three sub-patterns are identifiable. First, deliberate non-standard orthography (e.g., *salom* → *slaam*, *kel* → *keel*, *nima* → *nimaa*) signals informality, youth identity, and distance from normative school literacy. Second, emotive punctuation and capitalization: sequences of exclamation marks (!!!), question marks (???), combined marks (!?), and alternating capitalization (*Zo'R*, *ZO'R*, *zO'R*) convey heightened emotion and an ironic stance. Third, linguistic crossing—the temporary adoption of features associated with other social groups (e.g., using English discourse markers such as *well*, *so*, and *actually* in Uzbek sentences, or adopting features of Tashkent urban slang by speakers from other regions)—functions as a form of playful identity exploration. These patterns are not random errors but systematic pragmatic resources for constructing a youthful, digitally savvy persona.

Derivational patterns in youth speech show both continuity and innovation relative to standard Uzbek.

Several native Uzbek derivational suffixes have gained new productivity in youth speech. The suffix *-chi* (agent noun) now attaches to a wider range of bases, including English roots and novel forms: *laykchi* (someone who likes posts), *kommentchi* (commenter), *selfchi* (someone who takes many selfies). The suffix *-lik* (abstract noun) appears in innovative formations: *zo'rlik* (awesomeness), *toptirishlik* (perfection), *noflik* (the state of being “no” or negative). The suffix *-cha* (diminutive/approximative) extends to new contexts: *ozgina* (a little) → *ozchami* (just a tiny bit), *tez* (fast) → *tezchami* (just a little quickly). These extensions follow native morphological rules but apply them to new lexical material and convey new pragmatic nuances, often expressing endearment or understatement.

Emergence of Hybrid Formations (Uzbek + English). The most productive derivational pattern in the corpus is the combination of English lexical roots with Uzbek derivational suffixes. This pattern follows the template:

[English root] + [Uzbek suffix]

Frequent examples include (Table 1):

Table 1. Hybrid Uzbek–English Derivational Forms in Youth Speech¹

Hybrid form	English source	Uzbek suffix	Meaning
<i>like+la+moq</i>	like	-la (verbalizer)	to like
<i>post+la+moq</i>	post	-la (verbalizer)	to post
<i>share+la+moq</i>	share	-la (verbalizer)	to share
<i>block+la+moq</i>	block	-la (verbalizer)	to block
<i>repost+qil+moq</i>	repost	qil- (to do)	to repost
<i>selfi+chi</i>	selfie	-chi (agent)	selfie-taker
<i>story+chi</i>	story	-chi (agent)	story-poster

These hybrid forms are so frequent in the youth corpus that they appear to have become conventionalized for certain common digital actions. Notably, these hybrid verbs are fully conjugated with Uzbek tense/aspect markers: *like+la+dim* (I liked), *post+la+di* (he/she posted), *block+la+gan* (has blocked). This represents a departure from earlier borrowing patterns where English verbs were typically used uninflected (e.g., *like bosmoq* – to press like). The hybrid pattern suggests that young speakers are treating English roots as potential bases for native derivation, indicating a deeper level of integration than simple lexical borrowing [1].

Youth speech shows a preference for clipped forms (shortened words) and blends (combining parts of two words). Clipping examples:

telefon → *tel*, *kompyuter* → *komp*, *universitet* → *univer*, *Instagram* → *insta*, *Telegram* → *telega*.

Blends are less common but creatively formed: *salom* + *alik* → *salalik* (a playful greeting), *yaxshi* + *yomon* → *yaxyomon* (so-so, lit. good-bad), *bosh* + *miya* → *bomiya* (nonsense, lit. head-brain). These shortening strategies serve both communicative efficiency (faster typing) and in-group signaling (only those familiar with the clipping conventions understand).

The distribution of pragmatic and derivational features varies systematically across platforms, age subgroups, and gender.

Platform variation. Telegram comments show the highest frequency of compressed forms and clippings, reflecting the fast-paced, high-volume nature of Telegram group chats. Instagram shows the highest frequency of intensified evaluative language and emoji use, consistent with the platform's focus on visual-aesthetic content. YouTube comments show the highest frequency of playful identity construction (non-standard orthography, crossing), possibly because comment sections are more public and performative.

Age variation. The 16–19 age group shows the highest rates of all innovation features. Code-switching to English peaks in this group (average 12% of content words in posts, compared to 8% for 20–25 and 4% for 26–30). Hybrid verb formations (*like+la+moq*) are almost exclusively used by the 16–25 group. The 26–30 group shows more conservative patterns, closer to standard Uzbek but with some adoption of features that originated in the younger group. This suggests a generational gradient, with innovations originating in the youngest group and propagating upward as that group ages – though longitudinal data would be needed to confirm.

Gender variation. Minimal statistically significant gender differences were found in pragmatic patterns, but one area showed difference: the use of emotive punctuation (multiple exclamation marks, combined ?!) was approximately 1.5 times more frequent in messages identified as from female users. No significant gender differences were found in derivational patterns.

CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTIONS

This study has examined pragmatic and derivational changes in Uzbek youth speech based on a corpus of social media and media texts from 2022–2026. The findings demonstrate that young Uzbek speakers are actively reshaping their language in response to the affordances and constraints of digital communication. These changes are not superficial; they involve both new pragmatic strategies (compression, intensification, playful identity performance) and new derivational patterns (extended suffix productivity, hybrid formations, clippings and blends).

Several broader conclusions emerge. First, the changes documented here are systematic, rule-governed, and functionally motivated. The compression of expressive forms, for example, serves a real communicative need in fast-paced digital exchanges. The shift toward hybrid Uzbek-English derivations reflects the increasing centrality of English as a source of digital concepts while maintaining Uzbek morphological structure. These are signs of linguistic vitality, not decay.

¹ Source: Author's elaboration.

Second, youth speech functions as a laboratory for language change. Features that originate in the speech of the youngest cohort (16–19) appear to propagate to older cohorts (20–25) over time, suggesting that today's youth innovations may become tomorrow's general norms. Longitudinal tracking would be needed to confirm whether specific features stabilize and spread.

Third, there is a substantial gap between the Uzbek language as taught in schools (based on literary norms) and the Uzbek language as actually used by young people in digital spaces. This gap has pedagogical implications: if education ignores the linguistic reality of students' out-of-school communication, it risks becoming irrelevant or producing students who feel that their natural language use is stigmatized.

Based on these findings, the following suggestions are offered:

For language educators and curriculum developers:

1) Recognize that youth speech features (hybrid forms, clippings, intensified evaluation) are not errors but systematic variations appropriate to specific contexts. Teaching should focus on register awareness – helping students distinguish when innovative forms are appropriate (informal digital communication) versus when standard forms are expected (academic writing, official documents).

2) Incorporate authentic youth speech data into classroom materials, not to endorse all innovations as normative but to develop students' ability to analyze and reflect on language variation.

3) Bridge the gap between standard Uzbek and youth speech by explicitly teaching the derivational patterns that are productive in both (e.g., the suffix *-chi* works the same way in standard and innovative formations, just on different bases).

For lexicographers and dictionary compilers:

1) Consider documenting high-frequency hybrid forms (e.g., *likelamoq*, *postlamoq*) in digital or supplemental dictionaries, with clear labeling indicating their register (informal, youth, digital).

2) Document non-standard clippings and blends that have achieved widespread use (*tel* for telephone, *komp* for computer, *insta* for Instagram) as part of the expanding vocabulary of Uzbek, while clearly distinguishing them from standard forms.

In conclusion, the pragmatic and derivational changes observed in Uzbek youth speech are neither a crisis nor a cause for alarm. They are the normal, healthy manifestation of language adaptation to new communicative environments. Young Uzbek speakers are not destroying their language; they are, like generations before them, reshaping it to meet their needs. The challenge for educators, policymakers, and the broader society is not to prevent change but to manage it wisely – preserving the core grammatical and lexical resources of Uzbek while recognizing the creativity and communicative intelligence of its youngest speakers.

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